

Application of Gradient Correction to Neutron Diffusion Calculation based on Particle Method

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ABSTRACT

To facilitate the handling of a deformed geometry under an extraordinary situation (e.g., the severe accident progression and the fuel debris retrieval) in the multiphysics simulation, we are developing neutronics calculation methods using the particle method, such as the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method. In this study, we aim to reduce the analytical modeling error due to the SPH method (e.g., the kernel function type and the smoothing length) by implementing the gradient correction into a neutron diffusion calculation code based on the SPH method. Furthermore, we newly propose a simple method to treat the albedo boundary in the SPH-based diffusion code. To verify our prototype SPH-based neutron diffusion code for the calculation geometries with the irregular particle positions, a series of numerical calculations was carried out for a two-dimensional homogenized square core, where the spatial position of each particle was randomly and individually displaced. Consequently, we confirmed that the average value of the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} using the gradient correction agreed well with the reference value. The gradient correction is useful to reduce the dependence of k_{eff} on the kernel function type and the smoothing length, thus it is able to robustly solve the neutron diffusion equation based on the SPH method.

Keywords: Particle method, Smoothed-particle Hydrodynamics, Neutron diffusion, Gradient correction

1. INTRODUCTION

This study aims to improve the accuracy of a neutron diffusion calculation that can more easily handle a deformed geometry. Specifically, we try implementing the gradient correction [1] into our prototype neutron diffusion code based on the particle method [2–6] and verifying the effectiveness.

Multiphysics calculations that combine fluid dynamics, heat transfer, and neutron transport calculations are required for scenarios such as fuel debris retrieval operations or severe accident progression at the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant. In our previous study [7], we developed a neutron diffusion calculation code based on the SPH method [2], which is one of the particle methods and NOT the conventional abbreviation for “Super Homogenization” in reactor physics. Particle methods are effectively used in fluid dynamics and heat transfer calculations in a mesh-free manner. Using the SPH-based neutron diffusion code, we can now directly handle any calculation geometry obtained from the SPH-based fluid dynamics simulation, without approximating and converting the specific calculation geometry. For example, our previous study [7] performed the SPH-based neutron diffusion calculation for a deformed fuel geometry in water.

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Note, however, that our previous study [7] identified the following issues to be addressed: the numerical result (e.g., effective multiplication factor k_{eff}) by the SPH-based neutron diffusion code had high sensitivity with respect to the kernel function type and the smoothing length h .

To address the above issue, we aim to apply the gradient correction [1], which has effectively been used in the SPH-based fluid dynamics calculation, to our prototype SPH-based neutron diffusion code. Furthermore, we aim to develop a simple method for handling the albedo boundary condition in the SPH-based neutron diffusion code, which is an important topic not addressed in our previous study [7]. To verify our updated SPH-based neutron diffusion code, we carry out the numerical calculation for a two-dimensional homogenized square core configured by the particles with irregular spatial positions. Note that, in this study, we have not conducted the calculation for a deformed geometry using our updated SPH-based neutron diffusion code.

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 describes the gradient correction for the neutron diffusion equation based on the SPH method, followed by an explanation of the simple method to treat the albedo boundary condition in the SPH method. Section 3 presents the verification calculations for our updated SPH-based neutron diffusion code. Section 4 summarizes the concluding remark and the future research topic.

2. NUMERICAL THEORY

2.1. SPH-based Neutron Diffusion Calculation

The two energy group neutron diffusion equations are described as follows:

$$-\nabla D_1 \nabla \phi_1 + (\Sigma_{a,1} + \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}) \phi_1 = \Sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 1} \phi_2 + \frac{\chi_1}{k_{\text{eff}}} (\nu \Sigma_{f,1} \phi_1 + \nu \Sigma_{f,2} \phi_2), \quad (1)$$

$$-\nabla D_2 \nabla \phi_2 + (\Sigma_{a,2} + \Sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 1}) \phi_2 = \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2} \phi_1 + \frac{\chi_2}{k_{\text{eff}}} (\nu \Sigma_{f,1} \phi_1 + \nu \Sigma_{f,2} \phi_2), \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_g is the total neutron flux; k_{eff} is the effective multiplication factor; D_g represents the diffusion coefficient; $\Sigma_{a,g}$ and $\nu \Sigma_{f,g}$ are the macroscopic absorption and production cross sections, respectively; $\Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g}$ represents the macroscopic scattering cross-section from the g' group to the g group; χ_g is the fission spectrum; the subscripts g denotes the neutron energy group, and $g = 1$ and 2 mean the fast and thermal energy groups, respectively.

Let us consider that a target calculation geometry is approximated using N “particles,” which do NOT correspond to actual particulate materials and virtual representative calculation points in the SPH method. When the SPH method is applied to non-differential terms in Eqs. (1) and (2) (e.g., the absorption, scattering, and production reaction rates), they can be discretized as follows:

$$\langle \Sigma_{x,g} \phi_g \rangle_i^{\text{SPH}} = \sum_{j=1}^N V_j \Sigma_{x,g,j} \phi_{g,j} W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|), \quad (3)$$

where $\langle P \rangle_i^{\text{SPH}}$ represents the SPH-discretized value for a physical quantity P at the position of the i th particle; \mathbf{r}_i and \mathbf{r}_j represent the spatial positions of the i th particle and the j th neighboring particle, respectively; V_j represents the volume of the j th particle, e.g., $V_j = R^2$ where R is the particle size (or diameter) in the two-dimensional geometry. Each particle has values such as the macroscopic cross section $\Sigma_{x,g,j}$ and the neutron flux $\phi_{g,j}$. Using Eq. (3), the macroscopic nuclear

reaction rate $\Sigma_{x,g}\phi_g$ at position \mathbf{r}_i is calculated by summing the contributions from the macroscopic nuclear reaction rate $\Sigma_{x,g,j}\phi_{g,j}$ of j th neighboring particles. Here, the kernel function $W_h(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j|)$ is used to calculate a weighting factor based on the distance between positions \mathbf{r}_i and \mathbf{r}_j . In this study, the following Wendland quintic kernel function of Eq. (4) [4], the cubic spline kernel function of Eq. (5) [3], and the Poly6 kernel function of Eq. (6) [6] for two-dimensional geometry are used:

$$W_h(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{7}{\pi h^2} \left(1 - \frac{r}{h}\right)^4 \left(1 + 4\frac{r}{h}\right) & \text{if } r < h \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$W_h(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{40}{7\pi h^2} \left(1 - 6\left(\frac{r}{h}\right)^2 + 6\left(\frac{r}{h}\right)^3\right) & \text{if } r < \frac{h}{2} \\ \frac{40}{7\pi h^2} 2\left(1 - \frac{r}{h}\right)^3 & \text{if } \frac{h}{2} \leq r < h \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$W_h(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{4}{\pi h^8} (h^2 - r^2)^3 & \text{if } r < h \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where h is the smoothing length, representing the distance over which a target particle influences its neighboring particles. $W_h(r)$ is normalized so that the integral over the whole space is equal to unity. Therefore, in the two-dimensional case, the dimension of the kernel function $W_h(r)$ is inverse length squared.

On the other hand, since the leakage term in Eqs. (1) and (2) is expressed by the second-order differential term, another discretization formula is necessary to calculate the leakage term by the SPH method. Based on the SPH-discretization method [5] for the heat transfer calculation, this study utilizes the following SPH-discretization for the neutron leakage term:

$$\langle -\nabla D_g \nabla \phi_g \rangle_i^{\text{SPH}} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^N V_j \bar{D}_{g,ij} (\phi_{g,j} - \phi_{g,i}) \times \frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \cdot \nabla_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2}, \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{D}_{g,ij} \equiv \frac{2D_{g,i}D_{g,j}}{D_{g,i} + D_{g,j}}, \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{D}_{g,ij}$ represents the harmonic average of the diffusion coefficients of the i th and j th particles; and ∇_j represents the gradient with respect to \mathbf{r}_j . Equation (7) calculates the sum of neutron current contributions between i th and j th particles $\bar{D}_{g,ij}(\phi_{g,j} - \phi_{g,i})/|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|$ using the gradient of the kernel function $\nabla_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)$ and the unit relative position vector $(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)/|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|$.

Consequently, the SPH method numerically solves the balance equation between the neutron annihilation and production at each particle position. This approach is different from the conventional Finite Volume Method (FVM) because FVM solves the balance equation within each spatial mesh. Note that, as described in our previous study [7], a matrix-vector equation can be obtained by applying the SPH method to Eqs. (1) and (2). This matrix-vector equation is almost the same as that of the k_{eff} -eigenvalue problem in the conventional deterministic method, where the unknowns are k_{eff} and the eigenvector of neutron flux ϕ . Therefore, the k_{eff} -eigenvalue problem in the SPH method can also be solved using the iterative method such as the power method. In this study, the Wielandt iteration [8] was used to reduce the outer iterations.

2.2. Application of Gradient Correction

In the SPH method, the irregular spatial positions of particles will cause a systematic error between the true gradient and the numerical value approximated by the SPH discretization. To reduce this systematic error in the SPH-based fluid dynamics simulation, the gradient correction [1] has been proposed and effectively utilized. This section briefly explains the gradient correction, which was implemented in our prototype SPH-based neutron diffusion code to improve the calculation accuracy of k_{eff} with low sensitivity with respect to the type of kernel function $W_h(r)$ and the smoothing length h .

By applying the gradient correction to the SPH-based neutron diffusion calculation, the neutron leakage term shown in Eqs. (7) and (8) can be corrected as follows:

$$\langle -\nabla D_g \nabla \phi_g \rangle_i^{\text{corSPH}} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^N V_j \bar{D}_{g,ij} (\phi_{g,j} - \phi_{g,i}) \times \frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \cdot \mathbf{L}_i^{-1} \nabla_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2}, \quad (9)$$

where the inverse matrix \mathbf{L}_i^{-1} means the correction matrix to modify the numerical gradient of the kernel function $\nabla_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)$. For each particle, the matrix \mathbf{L}_i is calculated by

$$\mathbf{L}_i = \left[\sum_{j=1}^N V_j \{ -(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \otimes \nabla_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|) \} \right], \quad (10)$$

where the symbol \otimes represents the tensor product. For example, in the two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system, the position vectors can be expressed as $\mathbf{r}_i = (x_i, y_i)$ and $\mathbf{r}_j = (x_j, y_j)$; thus, each element of the matrix \mathbf{L}_i can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{L}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^N -V_j (x_j - x_i) \frac{\partial W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{\partial x_j} & \sum_{j=1}^N -V_j (x_j - x_i) \frac{\partial W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{\partial y_j} \\ \sum_{j=1}^N -V_j (y_j - y_i) \frac{\partial W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{\partial x_j} & \sum_{j=1}^N -V_j (y_j - y_i) \frac{\partial W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{\partial y_j} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

The conventional SPH method (e.g., Eqs. (3) and (7)) assumes that the integral of the kernel function over the whole space is equal to unity. By constructing the SPH method based on a first-order Taylor series expansion without this assumption, \mathbf{L}_i is derived. In other words, \mathbf{L}_i is defined so that the gradient of the kernel function corrected by \mathbf{L}_i^{-1} satisfies first-order accuracy of the Taylor series expansion.

In addition, the magnitude of the kernel function is also corrected in our prototype SPH-based neutron diffusion code. This correction is necessary because the summation of the kernel weights deviates from unity when the i th particle position is near the outer boundary or the particle positions are irregular. In the SPH method, the integral of the kernel function over the whole space (or within the smoothing length h) should be equal to unity for any particle arrangement. Therefore, the macroscopic nuclear reaction rate of Eq. (3) is corrected as follows:

$$\langle \Sigma_{x,g} \phi_g \rangle_i^{\text{corSPH}} = \sum_{j=1}^N \Sigma_{x,g,j} \phi_{g,j} \left(\frac{V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)} \right). \quad (12)$$

2.3. Boundary Condition

In the SPH method, the Dirichlet boundary condition can be expressed by placing “wall particles” outside the peripheral particles. For example, in the case of the zero-flux boundary condition, the value of the neutron flux at the wall particle is fixed to be zero. Note, however, that such a simple approach will cause the SPH discretization error because the zero-flux position is extrapolated by the particle radius $R/2$ outside the actual boundary.

To address the above-mentioned issue, this study newly proposes a simple method which can treat the albedo boundary condition [9] in the SPH-based neutron diffusion code by adjusting the diffusion coefficients of wall particles while their neutron flux is fixed to zero. For this purpose, let us consider the effective diffusion coefficient $D_{g,eff}$ for the albedo boundary condition in FVM. Here, the diameter R of the i th peripheral particle is regarded as the spatial mesh size of FVM. Then, $D_{g,eff}$ can be expressed by

$$D_{g,eff} = \frac{(1 - \alpha)D_{g,i}R}{(1 - \alpha)\frac{R}{2} + 2(1 + \alpha)D_{g,i}}, \quad (13)$$

where α means the albedo value: $\alpha = -1, 0$, and $+1$ correspond to the zero-flux, the vacuum (i.e., incoming neutron current is zero), and the reflective boundaries, respectively. By regarding $D_{g,eff}$ as $\bar{D}_{g,ij}$ in Eq. (8), we can derive that the diffusion coefficient for the j th wall particle should satisfy the following condition:

$$D_{g,j} = \frac{R}{4} \frac{1 - \alpha}{1 + \alpha}. \quad (14)$$

Namely, $D_{g,j} = +\infty, \frac{R}{4}$, and 0 correspond to the zero-flux, the vacuum, and the reflective boundaries, respectively.

3. NUMERICAL VERIFICATION

3.1. Calculation Conditions

To verify the effectiveness of the gradient correction implemented in our prototype SPH-based neutron diffusion code, numerical calculations were performed for a two-dimensional homogenized square core.

The calculation geometry was a bare square fuel with a side length of 60 cm. The bare square core geometry is approximated using fuel particles and wall particles in the SPH method. The diameter R of all particles in the SPH method was set to be 1 cm. To investigate the systematic error due to the irregular arrangement of the particles, which will be encountered in an actual fluid dynamics simulation result, a series of SPH calculations was conducted as the following procedures. First, fuel particles located within the square core region were arranged in a lattice so that the center-to-center distance between adjacent particles was 1 cm. The total number of fuel particles was 3,600. Next, each of the regularly arranged fuel particles was individually and randomly displaced (perturbed) within a circle with a radius of 0.1 cm at the center of the original position. This process indicates a state where adjacent particles overlap by approximately 10%, which is an expected phenomenon in fluid dynamics simulations based on the SPH method. Note that the peripheral fuel particles were not displaced. Furthermore, a sufficient number of wall particles were placed

outside the peripheral fuel particles to simulate the zero-flux boundary condition. Here, $\bar{D}_{g,ij} \approx 2D_{g,i}$ is obtained by setting $\alpha = -0.999999999$, following Eqs. (8) and (14). We prepared ten calculation geometries with randomly displaced particles to evaluate the sample mean and the sample standard deviation for the numerical results of k_{eff} .

The k_{eff} eigenvalues were obtained by the two energy group SPH-based neutron diffusion calculation in the two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system. The two-group cross section data for the fuel particle were quoted from those of the fuel region in the LMW (Langenbuch, Maurer, Werner) benchmark problem [10]. The smoothing length h was given within the range from 1.5 cm to 3.0 cm in 0.1 cm increments to investigate the impact of h on k_{eff} . Furthermore, three different kernel functions (i.e., Eqs. (4)–(6)) were used in these calculations to investigate the difference due to the kernel function type. In the Wielandt iteration [8], the shifted eigenvalue λ was set to be 0.9 so that λ was larger than k_{eff} . The number of outer iterations was 8. In each outer iteration, the neutron flux was numerically solved by a direct method based on SuperLU [11], which is a high-performance library for the LU decomposition of large-scale sparse matrices.

To compare with the reference value of k_{eff} , the following analytical solution can be solved based on the neutron diffusion equations (1) and (2) for this benchmark problem:

$$k_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\nu\Sigma_{f,1} + \nu\Sigma_{f,2} \frac{\Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}}{\Sigma_{a,2} + D_2 B^2}}{\Sigma_{a,2} + \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2} + D_1 B^2}, \quad (15)$$

$$B^2 = \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2, \quad (16)$$

where $a = 60$ cm represents the side length of the square fuel, and $\Sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 1} = 0$, $\chi_1 = 1$, and $\chi_2 = 0$ for the fuel region of the LMW benchmark problem. Consequently, the reference value of k_{eff} was evaluated as $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.78959$ based on Eqs. (15) and (16) with the cross section data of the LMW benchmark problem.

Figure 1. Center positions of fuel and wall particles.

3.2. Numerical Results

Figure 2 shows the numerical results of k_{eff} with and without the gradient correction for the regularly arranged fuel particles. The vertical axis represents the relative error with respect to the

reference value. When the gradient correction was not applied, the kernel function type and the smoothing length h had a strong impact on k_{eff} results. On the other hand, applying the gradient correction can dramatically reduce the relative error within 50 pcm for $1.5R \leq h \leq 2.2R$, regardless of the kernel function type.

Similar to Figure 2, Figure 3 shows the sample mean of k_{eff} for the 10 irregular arrangements of fuel particles. The error bar represents the standard deviation (1σ) of k_{eff} obtained from ten independent arrangements. Consequently, the gradient correction was able to reduce the systematic error of k_{eff} by approximately one-tenth. When $2.2R \leq h \leq 2.5R$, the relative error due to the irregular arrangement was suppressed to within approximately 100 pcm. It should be noted that as h increases, the sum of the kernel weights approaches unity. However, the relative error slightly increases because the discontinuity of the material boundary is approximated by a smooth shape. This trend is confirmed in Figure 2-ii) and Figure 3-ii) for $2.5R < h$.

Through these numerical results, we could confirm the effectiveness of the gradient correction in the SPH-based neutron diffusion code. In other words, the gradient correction should be applied to accurately calculate k_{eff} for regular and irregular particle arrangements in the SPH method.

i) without gradient correction

ii) with gradient correction

Figure 2. Relative error for the case of regular particle arrangement.

i) without gradient correction

ii) with gradient correction

Figure 3. Relative error for the case of randomly displaced particles.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the effectiveness of applying the gradient correction to the SPH-based neutron diffusion calculation method. Consequently, we demonstrated that the gradient correction could reduce the systematic error in k_{eff} due to the kernel function type and the smoothing length h , regardless of the particle arrangement.

A future research topic is the further application of the SPH method to the time-dependent neutron diffusion equation, where the delayed neutron effects are considered. For the verification, we need to solve typical kinetic benchmark problems such as the LMW transient problem.

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